

Using Mnemonics in Teaching German Vocabulary

Author(s): KHASANOVA OZODAKHON KURVONALI KIZI

Abstract:

Any language that is not a mother language is a foreign language for a person. In today's fast-paced and mobile world, there should be no foreign language for people. Knowledge of any foreign language other than the mother tongue is especially important in professional activities. It also affects a person's personal life. Knowledge of foreign languages is necessary in travel, as well as in private life. Learning a foreign language provides an opportunity to get acquainted with other cultures, mentalities, customs and traditions. This makes a person more open, flexible, and curious.

Keywords: mnemonics, vocabulary, foreign language, learning, teaching, German language, to memorize, active vocabulary, passive vocabulary, potential vocabulary, coding, remembering,

EASIJ

Accepted 25 August 2020

Published 31 August 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4031375

About Author

Author(s): KHASANOVA OZODAKHON KURVONALI KIZI
Fergana polytechnic institute, Uzbekistan.

Introduction

People take the first step towards consciously learning a foreign language mainly in primary school. Conscious learning of foreign languages requires a lot of time, effort, patience, regularity and systematization. At the same time, how to learn a foreign language easily and interestingly, what techniques will help in this, of course, is of interest to all foreign language teachers and language learners.

There are several goals in foreign language teaching, which are to develop listening comprehension, reading comprehension, speaking and writing skills. It is also important to have phonetics, vocabulary, grammar and spelling skills. Among them, the formation of teaching and learning techniques and skills is also important and requires special attention. Today, a foreign language teacher has the problem of directing students, language learners in general, to work independently, and in many cases it is ignored.

Vocabulary is a part of language learning. Mastering it is a necessary condition for foreign language communication. This is where many language learners face a problem. Below we will talk about ways to solve this problem using mnemonics, learning and teaching.

Vocabulary is defined in DUDEN as follows: die Gesamtheit der Wörter einer Sprache. That is, the set of words in a language is the vocabulary.

Vocabulary is important in the study of any foreign language and it is one of the foundations of the language learning process. Today, in our educational institutions, very few effective forms of increasing vocabulary are used in the process of language teaching. This is why language learners face great challenges in increasing their new vocabulary. Most words are simply memorized from a given list or memorized by the teacher. Even today, there are dictionaries of language learners, which usually consist of two columns. The first column contains the word in the foreign language, and the second column contains the language learner's native language translation. To verify that the word is memorized, the desired column is closed and its translation is said depending on the word in the second column. If no mistake is made in this process, the words are considered memorized. There are also few vocabulary-enhancing exercises in foreign language textbooks, focusing mainly on grammar exercises. To learn new words, a list of words in alphabetical order is given at the end of each chapter. For this reason, it is important for language learners to explore ways to increase vocabulary that are necessary but complex.

The structure of vocabulary

The set of words in a language constitutes the vocabulary of that language. It can be divided into different categories and classified according to it. According to Heyd, vocabulary is divided into two classes:

- an open class of vocabulary (nouns, verbs, adjectives) - representatives of this class are constantly enriched on the basis of development, adaptation to new needs, creation of new meanings and new words.
- a closed class of vocabulary (rhymes, articles, conjunctions, prefixes, etc.) - Representatives of this class have not been updated to date, although updated, their number is limited.

Heyd's next classification is a didactic classification, according to which vocabulary is divided into three classes:

- active vocabulary - this class includes all the words that a language learner can effectively master and use.
- passive (inactive) vocabulary - this class includes words that the language learner has previously learned, understands when reading and listening, but can't use effectively in speaking and writing;
- potential vocabulary - this class includes all words that the language learner does not know, but can understand according to the meaning of the components.

Today, mnemonics, which is an effective way to increase vocabulary in our educational institutions, is almost never used. Mnemonics is a method that makes it easier to remember, a quick way to the information we are looking for in our memory. It is associated with the concept of cognition, which is widespread today, and it can be argued that it is precisely the most effective of cognitive methods. With its help, the language learner will have the ability to memorize new learning material. There are different forms of mnemonics.

Methods

Most of Memory Psychologists note that there are three types of mnemonics:

1. Topological or logical type - in which the new information studied is associated with familiar objects;
2. Symbolic type - in which the data is memorized using numbers and letters;
3. Linked type - where the data is remembered by converting it into cross-linked words.

Memory techniques have been used in foreign language classes before. According to BIRKENBIHLOVÁ (1996, 43-44), such learning methods are rarely used in schools. Many students learn words by dry memorization, frequent repetition. Lessons usually try to impart grammar knowledge. Today, although action-oriented lessons have been offered by foreign stylists and have already entered foreign language classes, it is impossible to ignore grammar. But along with grammatical knowledge, having vocabulary is also very important. That is why it should be given great importance.

Memory methods involve the proper use of memory, and the elucidation of its functions is also important.

Memory is the ability of the nervous system of a living soul to store received information, which is necessary to organize the acquired information and retrieve it when necessary. In the process of learning, the result of information stored consciously or unconsciously appears in memory.

Memory storage of new data takes place in three stages.

1. **Coding.** This process is the process of storing new data in memory, in which the data is converted into certain codes. Data is stored in memory using a variety of forms, such as visual, acoustic, or semantic.

- visual form - image;
- acoustic form - audible information;
- semantic form - storage of meaning of information.

2. **Notice.** This means that the data is stored in memory for a certain period of time. Forgetting is characteristic for this stage, and a systematic study of the person with the goal is appropriate. That is, the information being studied should be reinforced by personal

application, feeling, experimentation, or association with various examples. Otherwise, this information is perceived by our brain as new information again.

3. **Remember** - the third step in which stored information can be used. There are two types:

1. Recognition: knowing the difference between new and familiar information;
2. Recycling: The process of rebuilding what is remembered.

The scientific literature cites several scholars who have dealt with word memorization techniques and strategies: Rampillon (1989), O'Malley / Chamot (1990), Oxford (1990), Wolff (1998). U. According to Rampillon, the process will consist of three phases:

Admission stage:

Vocabulary at the admission stage requires students to process three components: pronunciation, spelling, and meaning. The biggest challenge in learning vocabulary is making sense.

Understanding the meaning of a word in a foreign language can be done by a language learner as follows:

- Using the native language - The advantage of this technique is that all foreign language learners have their own native language and can use it at all levels.
- Using other Foreign Languages - This technique helps language learners who know at least two foreign languages to combine and understand both languages.
- Learning using planned language - When using this technique, language learners learn word formation techniques.
- Using International Foreign Words - A prerequisite for this technique is that language learners find it easier to understand the meaning of words.
- Using context - An unknown word can be understood depending on the text and sentence content.

Results

In addition, understanding the meaning of a word in a foreign language can be done using a bilingual dictionary. The use of dictionaries should be part of a learning process that requires and encourages language learners to work independently. Language learners should understand the dictionary not only as a means of explaining the meaning of a word, but also as a means of teaching spelling and pronunciation.

Conclusion

Mnemonics, on the other hand, makes the process of learning new words much easier. The basic principle of mnemonics is the transformation of the studied data into bright, resonant words or images, all of which are linked to previously known information. Any information is received by our brain through the senses: hearing, sight, full knowledge. The more sensory organs involved in the learning process, the better the information will be remembered. Along with perception, thinking also plays an important role in the human learning process. Logic and imagination also play an important role in learning.

References

- Birkenbihlová, V. F. (1996). Piliny v hlavě?: Návod k užívání mozku - od "majitelů mozku" k "uživatelům mozku". Hradec Králové: Svítání.
- Heyd, Gertraude (1990): Deutsch lehren. Grundwissen für den Unterricht in Deutsch als Fremdsprache. Frankfurt/M.: Diesterweg.
- Pressley, M.: Use of a mnemonic technique to teach young children language vocabulary. In: Contemporary Educational Psychology 6 (1981), 110-116.
- Raugh, M. R., & Atkinson, R. C. (1975). A mnemonic method for learning a second-language vocabulary. Journal of Educational Psychology, 67, 1-16.
- Review. Learning Disabilities Research, 23(1), 1-10.
- Vanlee Siriganjanavong. The Mnemonic Keyword Method: Effects on the Vocabulary Acquisition and Retention. English Language Teaching; Vol. 6, No. 10; 2013.

Cite this article: Cite this article:

Author(s), KHASANOVA OZODAKHON KURVONALI KIZI, (2020). "Using Mnemonics in Teaching German Vocabulary", **Name of the Journal**: Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 193 – 198. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4031375, Special Issue, Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 23, Month: August, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

Published By

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMIS)

